

Nirmala Alpha Gourava and Modified Nirmala Alpha Gourava Indices of Certain Dendrimers

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 24 May 2024 Corresponding Author: V.R.Kulli</p>	<p>In this paper, we introduce the Nirmalaalpha Gourava and modified Nirmala alpha Gourava indices and their corresponding exponentials of a graph. Also we compute the Nirmala alpha Gourava and modified Nirmala alpha Gourava indices of four families of dendrimers.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Nirmala alpha Gourava index, modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index, dendrimer.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

The graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ is a simple connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. For undefined term and notation, we refer the book [1].

A molecular graph is a graph in which the vertices correspond to the atoms and the edges to the bonds of a molecule. Several topological or graph indices [2] have been considered in Chemical Science and have found some applications, in *QSPR/QSAR* study, see [3, 4].

The Nirmala index [5] of a molecular graph G is defined as

$$N(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u) + d_G(v)}.$$

Recently, some Nirmala indices were studied in [6-20].

The first alpha Gourava index was defined by Kulli in [21] as

$$AGO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)].$$

Recently, some Gourava indices were studied in [22-39].

Motivated by Nirmala and first alpha Gourava indices, we introduce the Nirmala alpha Gourava index of a graph G as follows:

The Nirmala alpha Gourava index of a molecular graph G is defined as

$$NAGO(G)$$

$$= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}.$$

Considering the Nirmala alpha Gourava index, we define the Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of a graph G as

$$NAGO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}.$$

We define the modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index of a graph G as

$${}^m NAGO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}.$$

Considering the modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index, we introduce the modified Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of a graph G and defined it as

$${}^m NAGO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}}.$$

Recently, some topological indices were studied in [40, 41, 42, 43].

In this study, we compute the Nirmala alpha Gourava and modified Nirmala alpha Gourava indices of four families of dendrimers.

2. RESULTS FOR PORPHYRIN DENDRIMER $D_N P_N$

We consider the family of porphyrin dendrimers. This family of dendrimers is denoted by D_nP_n . The molecular graph of D_nP_n is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The molecular graph of D_nP_n

Let G be the molecular graph of D_nP_n . By calculation, we find that G has $96n - 10$ vertices and $105n - 11$ edges. In D_nP_n , there are six types of edges based on degrees of end vertices of each edge as given in Table 1.

Table 1. Edge partition of D_nP_n

$d_G(u), d_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(1, 3)	$2n$
(1, 4)	$24n$
(2, 2)	$10n - 5$
(2, 3)	$48n - 6$
(3, 3)	$13n$
(3, 4)	$8n$

Theorem 1. Let D_nP_n be the family of porphyrin dendrimers. Then

$$NAGO(G) = 2n\sqrt{13} + 24n\sqrt{21} + 10n\sqrt{12} + 48n\sqrt{19} + 13n\sqrt{27} + 8n\sqrt{37} - 5\sqrt{12} - 6\sqrt{19}.$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 1, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} NAGO(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)} \\ &= 2n\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)} + 24n\sqrt{1^2 + 4^2 + (1 \times 4)} \\ &\quad + (10n - 5)\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)} \\ &\quad + (48n - 6)\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)} \\ &\quad + 13n\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)} + 8n\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)} \\ &= 2n\sqrt{13} + 24n\sqrt{21} + 10n\sqrt{12} + 48n\sqrt{19} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ 13n\sqrt{27} + 8n\sqrt{37} - 5\sqrt{12} - 6\sqrt{19}.$$

Theorem 2. Let D_nP_n be the family of porphyrin dendrimers. Then

$$NAGO(G, x) = 2nx^{\sqrt{13}} + 24nx^{\sqrt{21}} + (10n - 5)x^{\sqrt{12}} + (48n - 6)x^{\sqrt{19}} + 13nx^{\sqrt{27}} + 8nx^{\sqrt{37}}.$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 1, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\ &= 2nx^{\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)}} + 24nx^{\sqrt{1^2 + 4^2 + (1 \times 4)}} \\ &\quad + (10n - 5)x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} + (48n - 6)x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\ &\quad + 13nx^{\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)}} + 8nx^{\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)}} \\ &= 2nx^{\sqrt{13}} + 24nx^{\sqrt{21}} + (10n - 5)x^{\sqrt{12}} \\ &\quad + (48n - 6)x^{\sqrt{19}} + 13nx^{\sqrt{27}} + 8nx^{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index of D_nP_n is

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G) &= \frac{2n}{\sqrt{13}} + \frac{24n}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{10n - 5}{\sqrt{12}} \\ &\quad + \frac{48n - 6}{\sqrt{19}} + \frac{13n}{\sqrt{27}} + \frac{8n}{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\ &= \frac{2n}{\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)}} + \frac{24n}{\sqrt{1^2 + 4^2 + (1 \times 4)}} \\ &\quad + \frac{10n - 5}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} + \frac{48n - 6}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\ &\quad + \frac{13n}{\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)}} + \frac{8n}{\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)}} \\ &= \frac{2n}{\sqrt{13}} + \frac{24n}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{10n - 5}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{48n - 6}{\sqrt{19}} + \frac{13n}{\sqrt{27}} + \frac{8n}{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of D_nP_n is given by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= 2nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{13}}} + 24nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{21}}} + (10n - 5)x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} \\ &\quad + (48n - 6)x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}} + 13nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}}} + 8nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{37}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$${}^m NAGO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2nx\sqrt{\frac{1}{1^2+3^2+(1\times3)}} + 24nx\sqrt{\frac{1}{1^2+4^2+(1\times4)}} \\
 &+ (10n-5)x\sqrt{\frac{1}{2^2+2^2+(2\times2)}} + (48n-6)x\sqrt{\frac{1}{2^2+3^2+(2\times3)}} \\
 &+ 13nx\sqrt{\frac{1}{3^2+3^2+(3\times3)}} + 8nx\sqrt{\frac{1}{3^2+4^2+(3\times4)}} \\
 &= 2nx\sqrt{13} + 24nx\sqrt{21} + (10n-5)x\sqrt{12} \\
 &+ (48n-6)x\sqrt{19} + 13nx\sqrt{27} + 8nx\sqrt{37}.
 \end{aligned}$$

3. RESULTS FOR PROPYL ETHER IMINE DENDRIMER PETIM

We consider the family of propyl ether imine dendrimers. This family of dendrimers is denoted by *PETIM*. The molecular graph of *PETIM* is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The molecular graph of *PETIM*

Let *G* be the molecular graph of *PETIM*. By calculation, we find that *G* has $24 \times 2^n - 23$ vertices and $24 \times 2^n - 24$ edges. In *PETIM*, there are three types of edges based on degrees of end vertices of each edge as given in Table 2.

Table 2. Edge partition of *PETIM*

$d_G(u), d_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(1, 2)	2×2^n
(2, 2)	$16 \times 2^n - 18$
(2, 3)	$6 \times 2^n - 6$

Theorem 5. Let *PETIM* be the family of propyl ether imine dendrimers. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAGO(G) &= 2 \times 2^n \sqrt{7} + 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} \\
 &+ 6 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} - 18\sqrt{12} - 6\sqrt{19}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 2, we deduce

$$NAGO(G)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)} \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n \sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)} \\
 &+ (16 \times 2^n - 18) \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)} \\
 &+ (6 \times 2^n - 6) \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)} \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n \sqrt{7} + 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} \\
 &+ 6 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} - 18\sqrt{12} - 6\sqrt{19}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. Let *PETIM* be the family of propyl ether imine dendrimers. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAGO(G, x) &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{7}} + 16 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{12}} \\
 &+ 6 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{19}} - 18x^{\sqrt{12}} - 6x^{\sqrt{19}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 2, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}} \\
 &+ (16 \times 2^n - 18) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} \\
 &+ (6 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{7}} + 16 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{12}} \\
 &+ 6 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{19}} - 18x^{\sqrt{12}} - 6x^{\sqrt{19}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 7. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index of *PETIM* is

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NAGO(G) &= \frac{2 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{7}} + \frac{16 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{12}} \\
 &+ \frac{6 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{19}} - \frac{18}{\sqrt{12}} - \frac{6}{\sqrt{19}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NAGO(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\
 &= \frac{2 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}} + \frac{16 \times 2^n - 18}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} \\
 &+ \frac{6 \times 2^n - 6}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\
 &= \frac{2 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{7}} + \frac{16 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{19}} - \frac{18}{\sqrt{12}} - \frac{6}{\sqrt{19}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 8. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of *PETIM* is given by

$${}^m NAGO(G, x) = 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{7}}} + (16 \times 2^n - 18) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} + (6 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}}.$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}} \\ &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}}} \\ &+ (16 \times 2^n - 18) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}}} \\ &+ (6 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}}} \\ &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{7}}} + (16 \times 2^n - 18) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} \\ &+ (6 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}}. \end{aligned}$$

4. Results for Poly Ethylene Amide Amine Dendrimer *PETAA*

We consider the family of poly ethylene amide amine dendrimers. This family of dendrimers is denoted by *PETAA*. The molecular graph of *PETAA* is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The molecular graph of *PETAA*

Let *G* be the molecular graph of *PETAA*. By calculation, we find that *G* has $44 \times 2^n - 18$ vertices and $44 \times 2^n - 19$ edges. In *PETAA*, there are three types of edges based on degrees of end vertices of each edge as given in Table 3.

Table 3. Edge partition of *PETAA*

$d_G(u), d_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(1, 2)	4×2^n
(1, 3)	$4 \times 2^n - 2$
(2, 2)	$16 \times 2^n - 8$
(2, 3)	$20 \times 2^n - 9$

Theorem 9. Let *PETAA* be the family of poly ethylene amide amine dendrimers. Then

$$NAGO(G) = 4 \times 2^n \sqrt{7} + 4 \times 2^n \sqrt{13} + 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} + 20 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} - 2\sqrt{13} - 8\sqrt{12} - 9\sqrt{19}.$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 3, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} NAGO(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)} \\ &= 4 \times 2^n \sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)} \\ &+ (4 \times 2^n - 2) \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)} \\ &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)} \\ &+ (20 \times 2^n - 9) \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)} \\ &= 4 \times 2^n \sqrt{7} + 4 \times 2^n \sqrt{13} + 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} \\ &+ 20 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} - 2\sqrt{13} - 8\sqrt{12} - 9\sqrt{19}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 10. Let *PETAA* be the family of poly ethylene amide amine dendrimers. Then

$${}^m NAGO(G, x) = 4 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{7}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\sqrt{13}} + (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\sqrt{12}} + (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\sqrt{19}}.$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 3, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\ &= 4 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)}} \\ &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} + (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\ &= 4 \times 2^n x^{\sqrt{7}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\sqrt{13}} \\ &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\sqrt{12}} + (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\sqrt{19}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 11. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index of *PETAA* is

$${}^m NAGO(G) = \frac{4 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{7}} + \frac{4 \times 2^n - 2}{\sqrt{13}} + \frac{16 \times 2^n - 8}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{20 \times 2^n - 9}{\sqrt{19}}.$$

Proof: We have

$${}^m NAGO(G)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\
 &= \frac{4 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}} + \frac{4 \times 2^n - 2}{\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (1 \times 3)}} \\
 &+ \frac{16 \times 2^n - 8}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} + \frac{20 \times 2^n - 9}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\
 &= \frac{4 \times 2^n}{\sqrt{7}} + \frac{4 \times 2^n - 2}{\sqrt{13}} + \frac{16 \times 2^n - 8}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{20 \times 2^n - 9}{\sqrt{19}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 12. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of *PETA*A is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= 4 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{7}}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{13}}} \\
 &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} + (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}} \\
 &= 4 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2 + (1 \times 2)}}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}}} \\
 &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}}} \\
 &+ (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}}} \\
 &= 4 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{7}}} + (4 \times 2^n - 2) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{13}}} \\
 &+ (16 \times 2^n - 8) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} + (20 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

5. RESULTS FOR ZINC PROPHYRIN DENDRIMER *DPZ_n*

We consider the family of zinc prophyridendrimers. This family of dendrimers is denoted by *DPZ_n*, where *n* is the steps of growth in this type of dendrimers. The molecular graph of *DPZ_n* is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The molecular graph of *DPZ_n*

Let *G* be the molecular graph of *DPZ_n*. By calculation, we obtain that *G* has $56 \times 2^n - 7$ vertices $64 \times 2^n - 4$ edges. In *DPZ_n*, there are four types of edges based on degrees of end vertices of each edge as given in Table 4.

Table 4. Edge partition of *DPZ_n*

$d_G(u), d_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(2, 2)	$16 \times 2^n - 4$
(2, 3)	$40 \times 2^n - 16$
(3, 3)	$8 \times 2^n + 12$
(3, 4)	4

Theorem 13. Let *DPZ_n* be the family of zinc prophyridendrimers. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAGO(G) &= 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} + 40 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} + 8 \times 2^n \sqrt{27} \\
 &- 4\sqrt{12} - 16\sqrt{19} + 12\sqrt{27} + 4\sqrt{37}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 4, we deduce *NAGO(G)*

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)} \\
 &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)} \\
 &+ (40 \times 2^n - 16) \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)} \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^n + 12) \sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)} \\
 &+ 4\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)} \\
 &= 16 \times 2^n \sqrt{12} + 40 \times 2^n \sqrt{19} + 8 \times 2^n \sqrt{27} \\
 &- 4\sqrt{12} - 16\sqrt{19} + 12\sqrt{27} + 4\sqrt{37}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 14. Let *DPZ_n* be the family of zinc prophyridendrimers. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAGO(G, x) &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\sqrt{12}} \\
 &+ (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\sqrt{19}} + (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\sqrt{27}} + 4x^{\sqrt{37}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 4, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\ &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} \\ &+ (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)}} + 4x^{\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)}} \\ &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\sqrt{12}} + (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\sqrt{19}} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\sqrt{27}} + 4x^{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 15. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava index of DPZ_n is

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G) &= \frac{16 \times 2^n - 4}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{40 \times 2^n - 16}{\sqrt{19}} \\ &+ \frac{8 \times 2^n + 12}{\sqrt{27}} + \frac{4}{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}} \\ &= \frac{16 \times 2^n - 4}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}} + \frac{40 \times 2^n - 16}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}} \\ &+ \frac{8 \times 2^n + 12}{\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)}} + \frac{4}{\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)}} \\ &= \frac{16 \times 2^n - 4}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{40 \times 2^n - 16}{\sqrt{19}} + \frac{8 \times 2^n + 12}{\sqrt{27}} + \frac{4}{\sqrt{37}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 16. The modified Nirmala alpha Gourava exponential of DPZ_n is given by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} \\ &+ (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}} + (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}}} + 4x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{37}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NAGO(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2 + d_G(u)d_G(v)}}} \\ &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2 + (2 \times 2)}}} \\ &+ (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2 + 3^2 + (2 \times 3)}}} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{3^2 + 3^2 + (3 \times 3)}}} \\ &+ 4x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{3^2 + 4^2 + (3 \times 4)}}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (16 \times 2^n - 4) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}} + (40 \times 2^n - 16) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{19}}} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n + 12) x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}}} + 4x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{37}}}. \end{aligned}$$

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel invariant is considered which is the Nirmala alpha Gourava index. The Nirmala alpha Gourava and modified Nirmala alpha Gourava indices of four families of dendrimers are determined.

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